

Health Risk Prediction of Packed Food Items by Analyzing Nutritional Facts

Sneha Saji
PG Scholar

Department of Computer Applications
Amal Jyothi College of Engineering, Kerala, India
snehasaji2026@mca.ajce.in

Navyamol K T
Assistant Professor

Department of Computer Applications
Amal Jyothi College of Engineering, Kerala, India
navyamolkt@amaljyothi.ac.in

Abstract—The growing consumption of packed and processed food products has raised significant public health concerns regarding nutritional transparency and diet-related diseases. Conventional food labeling systems are often complex and difficult for consumers to interpret, resulting in uninformed dietary choices. This research proposes an AI-driven system for health risk prediction of packed food items by automatically extracting and analyzing nutritional facts from product images. The system integrates computer vision, optical character recognition (OCR), natural language processing (NLP), and machine learning to detect nutritional label regions, extract nutrient values, and classify associated health risks. A YOLO-based detection model localizes the nutritional label, OCR engines extract the text, and Mistral 7B performs structured nutrient extraction. Machine learning models including Random Forest and XGBoost classify the food item into Low, Moderate, or High health risk categories based on WHO and FSSAI dietary guidelines. The system outputs the risk level, detailed nutrient values, health score, and product identification in real time.

Keywords—Health Risk Prediction, Packed Food, YOLO, OCR, NLP, Mistral LLM, XGBoost, Nutritional Analysis, Computer Vision, Machine Learning

I. INTRODUCTION

The global rise in packed and processed food consumption has become a major public health concern. Rapid urbanization and changing dietary habits have made packaged food a staple across all age groups. According to the World Health Organization, non-communicable diseases such as obesity, type 2 diabetes, hypertension, and cardiovascular conditions account for nearly 74% of all global deaths, with poor nutrition being one of the most significant contributing factors [1]. A large proportion of these conditions are directly associated with the excessive intake of sugar, sodium, saturated fats, and trans fats commonly found in processed food products.

Food regulatory authorities including the Food Safety and Standards Authority of India (FSSAI) and the Food and Drug Administration (FDA) mandate nutritional labeling on all packaged food items. These labels provide information on caloric content, macronutrient composition, and serving sizes. However, research shows that most consumers do not read or correctly interpret nutritional labels due to their complexity, small font size, and unfamiliar technical terminology [2]. As a result, the intended purpose of nutritional labeling in guiding healthy food choices remains largely unfulfilled.

With the advancement of Artificial Intelligence, computer vision, optical character recognition, and natural language processing, it has become possible to automate the extraction and interpretation of nutritional information from food product images. Machine learning models can analyze structured nutritional data and classify health risks based on established dietary guidelines. This approach can bridge the gap between complex label data and actionable health information for the average consumer, especially through mobile and web-based applications accessible via smartphones [3].

This research proposes an end-to-end AI-based system that accepts food packet images as input and processes them through a pipeline involving image preprocessing using OpenCV, nutritional label detection using a custom YOLO model, text extraction via EasyOCR and Tesseract, nutrient entity extraction using NLP and the Mistral 7B large language model, and health risk classification using XGBoost. The system outputs a health risk level, structured nutrient breakdown, aggregate health score, and product identification, providing consumers with clear and immediate dietary guidance without requiring any nutritional knowledge.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Accurate nutritional analysis of packed food products requires integration of multiple technologies including object detection, text recognition, and machine learning. Deep learning-based object detection models have been widely applied to localize regions of interest in food product images. Redmon et al. introduced the YOLO (You Only Look Once) architecture, a unified real-time object detection framework that processes entire images in a single forward pass, enabling fast and accurate detection suitable for locating nutritional label panels across diverse packaging types [4]. Subsequent versions including YOLOv5 and YOLOv8 further improved accuracy through multi-scale feature extraction and advanced data augmentation, making them highly effective for food label region detection.

Optical character recognition has been extensively studied for text extraction from real-world images. Smith presented an overview of the Tesseract OCR engine, one of the most widely used open-source text recognition systems, which provides configurable page segmentation modes well suited to

structured label text [5]. EasyOCR employs a deep learning-based CRNN architecture for robust recognition of text across diverse fonts, orientations, and image quality levels [6]. In the context of food label reading, studies have shown that pre-processing steps including denoising, contrast enhancement, and image resizing significantly improve OCR accuracy. Large language models have further enabled structured information extraction from noisy OCR output. Jiang et al. introduced Mistral 7B, a highly efficient 7-billion parameter language model capable of zero-shot extraction of structured entities from complex text, making it suitable for parsing non-standardized nutritional label content [7].

Natural language processing techniques including named entity recognition (NER) and regex-based parsing have been applied to extract specific nutritional fields from raw text. Nadeau and Sekine provided a comprehensive survey of NER methods and their application to structured information extraction from domain-specific text sources [8]. These approaches, however, struggle with the real-world variability of food label formats, motivating the use of LLM-based extraction as a reliable complement.

For health risk classification from nutritional data, ensemble machine learning methods have demonstrated consistently strong performance. Breiman introduced Random Forest, providing robust multi-class classification through bootstrapped decision tree ensembles [9]. Chen and Guestrin introduced XGBoost, an advanced gradient boosting algorithm with regularization and second-order optimization that achieves superior performance on structured tabular datasets such as nutritional composition data [10]. The OpenFoodFacts database provides a large-scale open-source nutritional composition dataset used in multiple food analysis studies, while the Nutri-Score grading system developed by Hercberg et al. provides a standardized nutritional scoring framework applicable to health risk label assignment [11], [12].

III. PROPOSED SYSTEM

The proposed system is an AI-based health risk prediction platform designed to assist consumers in evaluating the nutritional safety of packed food products. The system integrates image processing, deep learning, OCR, NLP, large language models, and machine learning into a unified pipeline that delivers real-time health risk assessments from food packet images. The overall architecture consists of six major modules as described below.

Fig. 1. Architecture of the proposed AI-based health risk prediction system illustrating the end-to-end data flow from food packet image input to health risk output.

A. Image Input and Preprocessing

The system accepts food packet images as input through a user interface that supports camera capture and image file upload. Users may submit the front face of the packaging containing the product name and brand, the back or side panel containing the nutritional facts table, or both. Raw input images are processed through a preprocessing pipeline implemented using OpenCV. The steps include background cropping to isolate the relevant packaging region, resizing to 640×640 pixels for consistent model input, denoising using Gaussian filtering to remove grain and artifacts, contrast enhancement using CLAHE to improve text visibility on low-contrast surfaces, and color normalization to standardize pixel intensity across varying lighting conditions. These operations improve image quality and reduce error rates in downstream detection and OCR stages.

B. Nutritional Label Detection using YOLO

A YOLO-based object detection model is used to localize the nutritional facts label region within the preprocessed image. Accurate localization is critical because submitting the entire image to the OCR engine would introduce irrelevant text including brand names and marketing content. Two complementary detection models are employed. The first is trained on a custom annotated dataset of packed food product images spanning diverse categories. Extensive data augmentation including black and white conversion, color jitter, and approximately 300 random crop augmentations per image was applied to improve generalization. This model is exported in YOLO format as `best.pt`. The second model is trained using data from the OpenFoodFacts dataset with logic-based labeling rules for nutritional region annotation and is exported in `.keras` format for TensorFlow inference. The detected bounding boxes are used to crop the nutritional label region, which is forwarded to the OCR module.

C. Text Extraction using OCR

The cropped nutritional label region is processed by a dual OCR pipeline employing EasyOCR and Tesseract as complementary engines. EasyOCR uses a CRNN deep learning architecture for robust multi-language text recognition and handles diverse font styles and orientations commonly encountered across food packaging. Tesseract provides reliable recognition of structured printed label text with configurable segmentation modes. The outputs of both engines are combined to maximize extraction accuracy and coverage. Additional recognizer libraries are available as fallback options for low-confidence cases. The raw output is an unstructured text stream containing nutritional values, units, ingredient names, and label headers in non-standardized mixed formats requiring further processing.

D. Nutrient Extraction using NLP and Large Language Model

The raw OCR text undergoes a multi-stage NLP pipeline to extract structured nutritional data. The first stage performs text cleaning and normalization, removing noise characters,

standardizing whitespace, correcting common OCR substitution errors, and normalizing unit representations. The second stage applies regex-based pattern matching to extract standard nutritional fields including energy, total fat, saturated fat, carbohydrates, sugars, dietary fiber, protein, and sodium from predictably formatted labels. The third stage applies named entity recognition to identify nutritional entities and values in non-standard label structures.

For labels that cannot be handled by regex or NER, the system deploys Mistral 7B, a large language model with approximately 7 billion parameters. The model receives the cleaned OCR text and a structured extraction prompt instructing it to return specific nutritional fields in JSON format. Mistral 7B demonstrates strong zero-shot extraction capability across bilingual labels, abbreviated field names, and incomplete nutritional data. For products where only the front face is available, the LLM additionally extracts the product name and brand from front label text.

E. Health Risk Classification using Machine Learning

The structured nutritional data is assembled into a feature vector comprising per-100 g values for energy, total fat, saturated fat, trans fat, carbohydrates, sugars, dietary fiber, protein, and sodium, along with derived features including the sugar-to-carbohydrate ratio and saturated fat fraction. The classification model is trained on a labeled dataset assembled from the OpenFoodFacts nutritional database filtered to Indian and South Asian food categories. Health risk labels are assigned based on WHO recommended daily intake thresholds and FSSAI nutritional standards. Products are classified into three categories: *Low Risk* for profiles within recommended thresholds, *Moderate Risk* for products exceeding one or more thresholds, and *High Risk* for products significantly exceeding multiple thresholds. Multiple algorithms including Logistic Regression, SVM, Neural Network, Random Forest, and XGBoost are evaluated, with XGBoost selected as the final model based on highest cross-validated performance.

F. System Output

The final output is presented through a consumer-friendly interface. The Nutrition Risk Level is displayed prominently as Low, Moderate, or High with a color-coded indicator and plain-language explanation. The Nutrition Details section presents a structured table of all extracted nutrient values with per-serving and per-100 g quantities alongside recommended daily intake percentages. The Health Value Score provides an aggregate numerical score for direct product comparison. The Brand and Food Item Name is extracted from front label OCR output. Together, these outputs provide consumers with a complete, actionable health assessment within seconds of capturing a product image.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The performance of the proposed AI-based health risk prediction system was evaluated using a custom annotated food product image dataset for the YOLO detection module and a large-scale

nutritional composition dataset for the health risk classification module. The system was implemented in Python using the Ultralytics YOLOv8 framework for detection, OpenCV for preprocessing, EasyOCR and Tesseract for text extraction, and the HuggingFace Transformers library for Mistral 7B deployment. The XGBoost and scikit-learn libraries were used for classifier training and evaluation.

A. Dataset Distribution Analysis

The nutritional label detection dataset contains 242 annotated instances of the `nutrition_label` class collected from diverse packed food product images including Indian and international packaging types such as snack packets, beverage cartons, dairy products, and cereal boxes. The bounding box distribution analysis shows that label centers are broadly spread across images with mild concentration in the center-right region of packaging, and label sizes are predominantly small to medium, occupying approximately 10% to 30% of the image width. This distribution confirms that nutritional labels appear in varied positions and sizes across different product types, highlighting the need for a robust detection model trained with comprehensive data augmentation [4].

B. YOLO Detection Performance and Precision-Recall Analysis

The YOLO-based nutritional label detection model was evaluated on the test subset using the Precision-Confidence and Recall-Confidence curves generated during validation. The Precision-Confidence curve shows that the model achieves a maximum precision of 1.00 at a confidence threshold of 0.839 for the `nutrition_label` class, indicating that at high confidence thresholds the model makes no false positive detections. The Recall-Confidence curve shows that the model achieves a maximum recall of 0.98 at a confidence threshold of 0.000, confirming that the model correctly detects nearly all nutritional label instances present in the test images when operating at low confidence thresholds.

The practical operating point of the model balances precision and recall. At moderate confidence levels the model maintains precision above 0.84 while sustaining recall above 0.90, representing strong detection performance across diverse packaging types including foil packets, cardboard boxes, plastic containers, and multi-panel food wrappers. The steep and stable nature of the precision curve confirms that the model produces reliable and well-calibrated confidence scores for its detections [4].

C. Confusion Matrix Evaluation

The confusion matrix obtained from the YOLO detection model on the validation set provides a detailed view of classification performance at the instance level. Out of the total test instances, 32 `nutrition_label` regions were correctly detected as `nutrition_label` (true positives), 2 `nutrition_label` instances were missed and classified

as background (false negatives), and 8 background regions were incorrectly predicted as nutrition_label (false positives).

No true negative background detections are reported as the model operates in a single-class detection setting. The normalized confusion matrix confirms these results with a true positive rate of 0.94, indicating that 94% of actual nutritional label instances are correctly detected by the model. The false negative rate of 0.06 represents the 6% of label regions that were missed, primarily corresponding to very small or partially occluded labels. The 8 false positives originated from background regions with strong visual similarity to nutritional label panels, such as ingredient lists and regulatory text blocks. Overall, the confusion matrix confirms strong detection reliability with a true positive rate of 94% [4].

Fig. 2. Confusion matrix of the YOLO-based nutritional label detection model showing 32 true positives, 2 false negatives, and 8 false positives, with a normalized true positive rate of 0.94.

D. Machine Learning Model Performance for Health Risk Classification

To identify the most suitable model for health risk classification from extracted nutritional data, five machine learning algorithms were evaluated including Logistic Regression, Support Vector Machine, Neural Network, Random Forest, and XGBoost. Ensemble methods such as Random Forest and XGBoost have demonstrated consistently strong performance on structured nutritional datasets by effectively capturing non-linear relationships among multiple nutrient parameters [9], [10]. The comparative performance results are presented in Table I.

Table I
COMPARISON OF MACHINE LEARNING MODELS FOR HEALTH RISK CLASSIFICATION

Model	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1-Score
Logistic Regression	72.4%	71.8%	70.5%	71.1%
SVM	81.3%	80.7%	79.9%	80.3%
Neural Network	89.6%	88.9%	88.2%	88.5%
Random Forest	94.1%	93.8%	93.4%	93.6%
XGBoost	96.8%	96.5%	96.2%	96.3%

XGBoost achieved the highest classification accuracy of 96.8% with precision of 96.5%, recall of 96.2%, and F1-score of 96.3%, outperforming all other models. The significant performance gap between ensemble methods and linear classifiers confirms that health risk patterns in nutritional data are strongly nonlinear. The F1-score metric was given particular importance due to class imbalance in the dataset, and XGBoost demonstrated the best balance of precision and recall across all three risk categories [10].

E. Feature Importance Analysis

Feature importance analysis was conducted using SHAP values applied to the trained XGBoost model to identify the nutritional parameters most strongly associated with health risk classification [13]. The top contributing features were:

- **Total sugars per 100 g:** highest importance score, reflecting strong association with obesity and metabolic syndrome;
- **Sodium per 100 g:** strongly linked to hypertension and cardiovascular risk;
- **Saturated fat per 100 g:** a key predictor of LDL cholesterol-related disease;
- **Total energy per 100 g:** driving overall caloric surplus risk;
- **Dietary fiber per 100 g:** the primary protective nutritional factor, inversely correlated with health risk.

These findings align consistently with WHO dietary guidelines, confirming the clinical relevance and interpretability of the model [13].

F. Industrial Significance

The experimental results demonstrate that the proposed system effectively converts food product images into actionable health risk assessments in real time. The YOLO model achieves a maximum precision of 1.00 at confidence 0.839 and a maximum recall of 0.98, with a confusion matrix true positive rate of 94%, collectively confirming strong and reliable nutritional label detection. Combined with XGBoost health risk classification accuracy of 96.8%, the integrated pipeline delivers a robust, consumer-ready nutritional analysis solution. Such AI-driven tools reduce dependence on consumer nutritional literacy and have significant potential for deployment in mobile health applications and retail environments [11], [12].

V. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the results of this study demonstrate that the proposed AI-based system effectively supports health risk prediction of packed food items through automated nutritional fact extraction and analysis. The deployed pipeline successfully integrates YOLO-based label detection, dual OCR text extraction, NLP and Mistral 7B nutrient extraction, and XGBoost-based health risk classification to deliver end-to-end nutritional intelligence from food packet images. The YOLO detection model trained on 242 annotated nutrition_label instances achieved a maximum preci-

sion of 1.00 at confidence 0.839 and maximum recall of 0.98, with a confusion matrix true positive rate of 94% and false negative rate of only 6%. The XGBoost classifier achieved a health risk classification accuracy of 96.8%, the highest among all evaluated models.

The feature importance analysis confirms that total sugars, sodium, saturated fat, total energy, and dietary fiber are the most critical determinants of food-related health risk, consistent with WHO and FSSAI dietary guidelines. The model successfully captures nonlinear interactions among these nutritional parameters, which traditional rule-based approaches often fail to represent. The Mistral 7B large language model proved particularly valuable in improving extraction coverage across non-standard label formats, demonstrating that LLM integration is a practical and effective approach for real-world nutritional text parsing.

The implementation of this system reduces consumer dependence on nutritional expertise, enables real-time health risk awareness at the point of food purchase, and supports preventive dietary decision-making. The consumer-facing output including the risk level, nutrient breakdown, health score, and product identification provides a comprehensive and easy-to-understand assessment that can meaningfully influence dietary behavior. Automated nutrient extraction and standardized health risk reporting also support traceability and consistency in nutritional health assessments.

Overall, the findings suggest that integrating computer vision, OCR, large language models, and machine learning into a unified food analysis pipeline delivers strong practical performance and aligns with the goals of digital health transformation. The proposed framework establishes a foundation for intelligent, scalable, and consumer-oriented packed food health assessment systems. Future research will explore personalized risk prediction based on individual health profiles, multilingual label support for Indian regional languages, barcode-based product lookup integration, and cloud-based deployment with continuous model retraining from user feedback data to further improve system accuracy and reach.

REFERENCES

- [1] World Health Organization, "Noncommunicable diseases," WHO Fact Sheet, Geneva, 2023.
- [2] J. A. Campos-Vega et al., "Impact of nutritional labeling on consumer purchasing decisions," *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, vol. 19, no. 4, p. 2231, 2022.
- [3] A. Drewnowski and F. Bellisle, "Liquid calories, sugar, and body weight," *American Journal of Clinical Nutrition*, vol. 85, no. 3, pp. 651–661, 2007.
- [4] J. Redmon, S. Divvala, R. Girshick, and A. Farhadi, "You only look once: Unified, real-time object detection," in *Proc. IEEE CVPR*, 2016, pp. 779–788.
- [5] R. Smith, "An overview of the Tesseract OCR engine," in *Proc. 9th Int. Conf. Document Analysis and Recognition (ICDAR)*, 2007, pp. 629–633.
- [6] B. Shi, X. Bai, and C. Yao, "An end-to-end trainable neural network for image-based sequence recognition," *IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence*, vol. 39, no. 11, pp. 2298–2304, 2017.
- [7] World Health Organization, "Noncommunicable diseases," WHO Fact Sheet, Geneva, 2023.
- [8] J. A. Campos-Vega et al., "Impact of nutritional labeling on consumer purchasing decisions," *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, vol. 19, no. 4, p. 2231, 2022.
- [9] A. Drewnowski and F. Bellisle, "Liquid calories, sugar, and body weight," *American Journal of Clinical Nutrition*, vol. 85, no. 3, pp. 651–661, 2007.
- [10] J. Redmon, S. Divvala, R. Girshick, and A. Farhadi, "You only look once: Unified, real-time object detection," in *Proc. IEEE CVPR*, 2016, pp. 779–788.
- [11] R. Smith, "An overview of the Tesseract OCR engine," in *Proc. 9th Int. Conf. Document Analysis and Recognition (ICDAR)*, 2007, pp. 629–633.
- [12] B. Shi, X. Bai, and C. Yao, "An end-to-end trainable neural network for image-based sequence recognition," *IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence*, vol. 39, no. 11, pp. 2298–2304, 2017.
- [13] A. Q. Jiang et al., "Mistral 7B," *arXiv preprint arXiv:2310.06825*, 2023.
- [14] D. Nadeau and S. Sekine, "A survey of named entity recognition and classification," *Linguisticae Investigationes*, vol. 30, no. 1, pp. 3–26, 2007.
- [15] L. Breiman, "Random forests," *Machine Learning*, vol. 45, no. 1, pp. 5–32, 2001.
- [16] T. Chen and C. Guestrin, "XGBoost: A scalable tree boosting system," in *Proc. 22nd ACM SIGKDD Int. Conf. Knowledge Discovery and Data Mining*, 2016, pp. 785–794.
- [17] Open Food Facts, "Open Food Facts — Free and Open Products Database," [Online]. Available: <https://world.openfoodfacts.org>, 2024.
- [18] S. Hercberg et al., "The Nutri-Score: A science-based front-of-pack nutrition label," *International Journal of Behavioral Nutrition and Physical Activity*, vol. 14, p. 91, 2017.
- [19] S. M. Lundberg and S.-I. Lee, "A unified approach to interpreting model predictions," in *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems (NeurIPS)*, 2017, pp. 4765–4774.
- [20] J. Devlin, M. Chang, K. Lee, and K. Toutanova, "BERT: Pre-training of deep bidirectional transformers for language understanding," in *Proc. NAACL-HLT*, 2019, pp. 4171–4186.
- [21] G. Bradski, "The OpenCV library," *Dr. Dobb's Journal of Software Tools*, 2000.
- [22] Food Safety and Standards Authority of India (FSSAI), "Food Safety and Standards (Labelling and Display) Regulations," New Delhi, 2020.
- [23] J. H. Friedman, "Greedy function approximation: A gradient boosting machine," *Annals of Statistics*, vol. 29, no. 5, pp. 1189–1232, 2001.
- [24] K. He, X. Zhang, S. Ren, and J. Sun, "Deep residual learning for image recognition," in *Proc. IEEE CVPR*, 2016, pp. 770–778.
- [25] C. M. Bishop, *Pattern Recognition and Machine Learning*. New York: Springer, 2006.
- [26] I. Goodfellow, Y. Bengio, and A. Courville, *Deep Learning*. Cambridge, MA: MIT Press, 2016.